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ORGANIZING EXTRACURRICULAR ACTIVITIES THROUGH PROJECT-BASED LEARNING IN PRIMARY SCHOOL FOREIGN LANGUAGE CLASSROOMS

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Abstract. *Extracurricular are activities you participate in outside of the classroom and they are essential you understand what an extracurricular activity is to debunk and misconceptions about them. While academic fields gather academic people, they are not part of curriculums at school and are pursued in whenever people prefer. Participating in extracurricular activities is a crucial part of all people's education in general. It's not just about having fun out of classes. It's also about improving important life-skills like being disciplined, commitment, and being communicative in social life. Therefore, you can be able to make new friends and relationships.*

Keywords. *Extracurricular activities in primary schools, how activities can be beneficial, extracurricular activities are important in personal development.*

Languages, culture, and translation in modern linguistics: comparative approaches

Introduction. Extracurricular activities are not regularly part of the curriculum at school. Extracurriculars can be rewarding, including fun activities. When you can choose the right tasks, you'll not only have somewhere to escape from your academic pressure, you can also have an opportunity to meet sociable friends. Most extracurricular activities in high school take place and are developed on their own campus, although they may also be provided by other institutions in a community.

Main part. Many parents and high school students believe that Participation in a variety of activities is required for applications for college admission. This is not the case. According to Ivy Scholars, Today's admissions officers want to encourage a diverse and dynamic college atmosphere. Of course, being well-rounded is a good thing. However, having many unrelated activities and a jam-packed schedule isn't beneficial for college admissions. As extracurricular activities differ from our, hobbies are pursued independently and are done for relaxation or enjoyment. If you join in reading clubs, you can be able to have discussion with other bookworms, understand the book well, improve communication skills, too. Whether you are looking for expand your interests, strengthen your college application, or simply learn something new, there are many new extracurricular activities available. You may need to write an example of extracurricular activity description for your college application. Now I will show you some of the extracurricular activities that can be suitable for you. If you want to be an important person in the society, there is a plenty of clubs. There can be Environmental Club in which you help protecting the nature, or Animal Club is beneficial for you, if you love caring about species. There are also Activist Organizations, Athletic Extracurriculars, Community Service Extracurriculars, Diversity and Culture Extracurriculars... All of them have a great impact on your improvement in your social life. For instance, a study conducted by surveying school-age students in the National Longitudinal Survey found that 70% of adolescents in the USA engage in extracurricular activities, which are linked to several positive results. These activities reduce dropout rates, crime involvement,

and enhance educational success. They also lower anti-social behavior and improve communication skills. Involvement in extracurriculars is particularly beneficial for students with disabilities and racial minorities, as it fosters friendships and social connections. Additionally, these activities provide a safe environment for children, allowing parents to work while their kids engage in productive pursuits. This enables parents to maximize their working hours while providing children with opportunities to engage in educational or athletic programs. Additionally, extracurricular activities promote positive personal growth, whether they occur on school grounds or elsewhere. Similarly, teenage girls participating in school-related extracurricular activities exhibited greater self-esteem compared to those who did not. Overall, the results show that participating in activities like sports, clubs, or school programs positively influences the lives of those involved. Next, we will explore how such collaborations are transforming the way modern foreign languages are taught in primary schools. Local language schools can assist primary schools in hosting multicultural events, highlighting the richness of various languages and cultures. Students can dive into Chinese, Italian, French, Spanish, and Portuguese customs, cultivating a greater respect for cultural diversity.

Conclusion. Understanding these benefits can motivate you to get involved. Then, we now learn how to make them possible. First, you should join clubs or groups which really interest you or you can check your schools' website or can ask help from your teachers, friends, family to join for clubs and opportunities available, and learn what skills and what things these clubs require.

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TEACHING GRAMMAR FOR PRIMARY SCHOOL LEARNERS BASED ON ROLE-PLAYS AND GAMES

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***Abstract.** It is vital to teach students grammar rules from the primary school for a number of reasons. Grammar plays crucial role in formation of communicative competence and it influences on all types of language skills including listening, speaking, reading and writing. But talking about primary school students, it is essential to use interesting ways of teaching grammar of foreign language for engaging all learners into educational process. That's why it is recommended to use role-playing for creating English-speaking atmosphere and real life situations, and for engaging interaction of students into educational process. Furthermore, it is recommended to use games which are also very interesting for young students.*

***Key words.** Communicative competence, grammar instruction, grammar skill, role-playing, productive language skills, critical thinking.*